

MODERN EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES IN THE CONTEXT OF A CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM: ENSURING EDUCATION QUALITY IN LINE WITH LABOR MARKET DEMANDS

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Abstract. *One of the reforms in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the acknowledgment of the impact of Professional Standards created within the framework of National Qualifications, which align with international standards, on enhancing education quality. This recognition has been substantiated comprehensively at the expanded videoconference meeting held on June 20, 2024, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev.*

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It follows that the quality of education is a fundamental factor in shaping human capital to cultivate a new generation capable of meeting the high demands of the contemporary labor market. Moreover, the role of Professional Standards and modern pedagogical technologies in organizing collaborative activities among producers, educators, and learners, as well as the international recognition of the national system for evaluating skills and knowledge, are essential matters that address the essence of organizing the educational process within the context of a credit-module system.

The establishment of modern educational practices in line with international standards under the credit-module system is recognized as a contributing factor to improving education quality.

At the same time, one of the positive aspects of the credit-module system that has contributed to enhancing education quality is the significant emphasis on the effective organization of modern educational practices. Clear organization of modern educational activities within the credit-module system is considered one of the factors for improving education quality. In most higher education institutions, students have information only about the names of subjects taught in that semester, the names of teaching staff, and the schedule and locations of classes shortly before the beginning of the semester. However, little information is provided to students regarding the objectives of these subjects, their role in the students' professional development, and the knowledge, skills, and competencies expected to be acquired through these courses. This lack of systematic, coherent, and transparent information about the subjects in higher education institutions is a matter of concern.

Under the credit-module system, each educator will have a subject syllabus, which will be presented to students at the beginning of the semester. The syllabus should include the objectives of the course, its significance within the educational program, the relevance for the students' future

professional activities, what students will be able to do as a result of studying the course, topics to be covered during the semester, a list of recommended literature, and evaluation criteria.

For elective subjects, the importance of such information for students is particularly high, as knowing only the course title or the name of the instructor is insufficient for making informed decisions regarding course selection. Students need to have adequate information about the course to arrive at such decisions. However, it should be particularly noted that when forming elective courses, it is advisable to consider the subjects that specialists will require in the future, even three, five, or ten years down the line, when they graduate in this field.

Another important aspect is the necessity to create opportunities for students to select elective subjects transparently at higher education institutions, which will also allow professors and educators to be selective.

This aspect highlights the foundational role of the credit-module system in the field of education and training within higher education institutions, especially as it pertains to organizing educational activities efficiently.

Nowadays, the concept of a modern lesson or educational activity is often mentioned in pedagogy. What kind of lesson is modern training? It is quite natural to ask this question. Pedagogical training is the main organizational form of education in higher education, it is a didactic event organized in a strict order with a permanent student body and aimed at a specific goal, and consists of lectures, practical classes, seminars, laboratories, independent work and independent education.

In modern educational training, the teacher skillfully uses the existing capabilities of the student, uses his mental potential and ensures its development, and the student, in turn, deeply assimilates knowledge and becomes competitive personnel and strives for excellence. Improving the quality and effectiveness of the educational process largely depends on how much training is provided with educational methods and means. These are any tools that transmit information, which provide knowledge that must be taught and studied. In some cases, the teacher also needs an educational tool designed for the student. The selected method, form and tools should complement each other. According to their characteristics, educational tools are divided into printed, technical and real, which, in turn, are divided into six types. These are:

- to receive and process information - text (curriculum ("program"), special textbook, lecture text, handouts and checklists);

- to create a general idea - visual (photograph, diagram, table, poster and images);

- to create a figurative and sound perception of processes - audiovisual (video film, compact disc, audio cassette, Power Point materials, electronic textbooks);

- for writing and saving images and text - assistant (board, pinboard, with a video projector screen, computer, flipchart, VCR, TVs);

- to form an idea of it through a model of the object being studied - a model (model, simulator, mannequin);

- tools, machines, semi-finished and finished products, raw materials can be used to create a real picture of the objects being studied.

In theoretical classes, teachers use mainly text and auxiliary means, and in practical classes - more visual and realistic ones.

The following can be indicated as the main criteria for organizing modern training. In particular:

training is focused on the personality of the student, based on active interaction between the teacher and the student;

training is carried out on the basis of the process of differentiation and approach to personal abilities;

training is focused on a high level of interest, desire, mental activity, academic performance of the student;

educational training is based on various methods and means depending on the content of the educational material;

attention is paid to activating the student's mental activity during the lesson;

the lesson fully uses the mechanism aimed at developing the student's personality, first of all, the student's ability to manage himself, thereby increasing his interest and desire for knowledge;

types of control are used to ensure training, quality and efficiency;

educational preparation, time is used effectively and purposefully;

attention is paid to easy assimilation of the educational material;

in training, theory and practice are interconnected.

The main features of modern educational preparation are as follows. That is:

a systematic approach to training ensures the gradual development of the student and his complete mastery;

training is aimed at fulfilling the social order of society;

it is ensured that the pedagogical activity of the teacher and the student is organized on the basis of the latest achievements of pedagogy and psychology;

in the process of training, educational and developmental tasks are solved based on the interests of the student;

learning ability, initiative, creative potential of the student are included;

the educational content will be optimized and the structure of the training will be improved;

the educational goals are clear, the educational process is colorful, which determines a high level of emotional tension of the lesson.

Educational tools used in organizing modern training can be divided into the following groups:

organizational tools for the implementation of pedagogical technologies;

educational technologies, teaching and methodological and didactic materials;

information, information and communication educational technologies and technical training tools.

The organizational tools for organizing a modern lesson can include the following documents: a reference manual for a first-year student; Regulations on the rating system; Regulations on the expulsion and resettlement of students; Orders of the OO'MTV on the implementation of pedagogical technologies in education.

The teaching technologies used in organizing modern training can include:

materials on the theory and methods of teaching academic subjects;

State educational standard, curricula and scientific programs, curricula and scientific programs in the field of education;

a methodological system for teaching subjects;

educational and methodological complexes of sciences;

independent work of a student and independent educational program and content;
plan and instructions for organizing independent work of a student under the guidance of a teacher;

rating control tasks or problems and tests;

textbooks on practical classes, teaching aids, educational projects, lecture notes, letters of recommendation and methodological instructions for independent work and electronic textbooks.

Didactic materials: classical didactic principles expressed, defined and formulated by leading philosophers, educators and psychologists; special methodological principles relevant in teaching technology; scientific principles that guide the teaching or training of students.

We include into information, information and communication technologies: everything related to obtaining information; reference book, demonstrated educational materials; use of a computer and other technical means; Internet.

Technical training tools are: computers; other technical means (interactive boards, duplicating equipment, etc.).

Rapid progress in the use of information and technological teaching aids has revealed the following new problems:

constantly expanding informatization and computerization of the educational process, development of forms of quality control;

changes in learning and teaching technology;

the influence of computer and telecommunication technologies on the information support of the educational process.

Accordingly, we note that information technologies cannot develop without information carriers that include all the necessary components. These components are the knowledge base, information resources, modern information communications and information service systems, computers and software, and the most important is the availability of knowledge and specialists in the field of computer science, information technology and engineering. Therefore, an important role is played by the formation of an appropriate educational information and educational environment, which is considered the most necessary element of the entire educational system. It is impossible to implement continuous education without individualization of education, without creating an individual educational program for each student.

This requires not only new approaches to the development of curricula, programs, principles of organizing the educational process, the use of new teaching and learning methods, but also the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies in education. We will witness the emergence of many new educational methods and forms of organization aimed at new types of educational activities, achieving new educational results (role-playing games, educational and cognitive structures, modular educational system, etc.). Therefore, it is necessary to include them in the set of tools of professional activity of teachers of these subjects.

Without using the following tools, it is impossible to bring educational activities to a qualitatively new, innovative level, ensuring the intensification and optimization of the educational process:

distance learning technologies (cases, Web-learning method, e-mail, videoconferencing, etc.), based on the unification of individual and collective organization of educational activities;

computer, hardware (digital photo and video cameras, scanners, media projectors, all equipment designed to receive and visualize information, etc.) and software;

educational electronic publications and resources based on the synthesis of information technologies (multimedia shows (presentations), electronic textbooks, Web resources of the educational institution, etc.);

modern computer and interactive projection technologies (interactive whiteboard, multi-screen pedagogical technologies, videoconferencing methods, etc.) [2].

Information and communication technologies can play a leading role in the integration of educational methods, organizational forms and tools, and their implementation in education is one of the important areas of education modernization. Electronic textbooks, new information, informative educational environment, educational teleconferences and other resources, the Internet - all these are means of organizing and implementing a new type of independent educational activity. In fact, it is necessary to create a new learning and teaching environment focused on independent learning activities of students and the development of their creative abilities.

Improving the quality and effectiveness of the educational process largely depends on the form of training and the degree of its provision with educational tools.

Thus, it was noted that the effective organization of educational training depends on the effectiveness of educational tools used in the learning process.

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